

THE ROLE OF NATURE TOURISM IN THE FORMATION OF ECOAESTHETIC THINKING IN YOUTH

Karshi State University

teacher **Niyazov Sobirjon Sodiqovich**

Annotation: Philosophical problems of using nature tourism in the formation of eco-aesthetic thinking in young people are analyzed in the article. In this, ecotourism, which has been developed with special attention in recent years in the whole world, including in Uzbekistan, the opportunities, current problems, prospects of nature tourism, as well as the role of young people in the development of aesthetic taste and aesthetic worldview have been researched.

Key words: ecoaesthetics, ecoaesthetic thinking, recreation, nature tourism, aesthetic taste, natural resources, patriotism, beauty, grandeur, elegance, aesthetic pleasure, health.

According to the UN World Tourism Organization, ecotourism is one of the five main strategic areas of tourism development until 2020. In recent years, the share of ecotourism in the total volume of the global tourism industry has exceeded 10 percent, and its growth rate is 2-3 times higher than the corresponding indicators in the entire tourism industry. Today, in scientific and popular literature, as well as mass media, many views and ideas aimed at revealing the role and importance of ecotourism, its economic and cultural opportunities are being put forward. In this article, we will try to philosophically analyze the formation and development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan in its own form and content, the aesthetic issues of the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan, and the importance of ecotourism in the formation of the aesthetic worldview of young people. The term ecotourism was first used in the 80s of the 20th century by the Mexican ecologist Hector Ceballos Lascurain at one of the international conferences dedicated to solving environmental problems. His idea was to create harmony between ecology and nature recreation.

This idea became very popular in its time and was supported by many people. The term recreation is Lat. recreation means restoration. Nature recreation is a set of comprehensive measures of health improvement, which involves the realization of people's exhaustion, health and work ability in harmony with nature, in the bosom of nature. We can include treatment in sanatoriums and spas, nature tourism, fishing, recreational sports related to nature. In the 60s of the 20th century, recreation began to rapidly enter medicine. According to Hector Ceballos Lascurain, the role of ecotourism in nature recreation is incomparable. In this, it means that nature and society will benefit equally through the rational, rational use of natural resources. That is, it is emphasized that people should treat nature with caution, not exploit its resources rudely, and in return, nature will give people physical and mental strength and health, and they will have aesthetic and physical rest by getting away from the noise and intensity of the city and bathing in the silence in the bosom of nature. Experts have given several definitions to the phenomenon of ecotourism. One of the most common of them is, "Ecotourism is to enjoy the natural and aesthetic possibilities of the environment while treating it with care and responsibility, thereby bringing economic benefits to the local population."¹In the development of ecotourism, local residents are interested in preserving the original state of nature, preserving the beauty of nature by limiting artificial interventions, and protecting the integrity of the ecosystem. Because it is financially beneficial for them. The most important aspect in this is to preserve the naturalness and original state of the natural environment, to protect its unique monuments, fauna and flora. "In recent years, favorable conditions have been created for the development of the tourism potential of the republic and the active attraction of investments in this field. At the same time, the potential of the country's water reservoirs as tourism demonstration objects and recreation zones has not been fully utilized, conditions for the implementation of business activities have not been created in their territory. In order to solve the accumulated problems in this field, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to improve the procedure for the development

of ecotourism and water protection zones of reservoirs" was adopted. At this point, The question arises as to what factors make the development of ecotourism important and relevant in the Republic of Uzbekistan. There are several factors to this:

-firstly, according to the information of organizations and institutions of international status, most types of tourism are increasing by an average of 5% per year, while the weight of ecotourism is increasing by an average of 20-30% per year. The scientific experience and conclusions of many experts and researchers show that, despite the fact that ecotourism is a new and young direction of tourism, its popularity is 2-3 times faster and faster than other tourist destinations; year.

- secondly, a base of certain achievements and experiences has been formed in Uzbekistan for the types of tourism, such as historical tourism, religious tourism, and cultural tourism, whose potential has not yet been fully developed;

- thirdly, more than 800 tour operator companies, about 600 hotels, more than 30 protected areas (reserves, national parks, rare natural monuments, etc.), 60 forestry farms are operating in Uzbekistan. There are also more than 400 unique natural monuments in Uzbekistan. These factors indicate that there is a high potential for the development of ecotourism in Uzbekistan, and the rational use of this potential is extremely beneficial for the economy of our country.

The main goals of ecotourism development are as follows:

- to demonstrate the ecotourism potential, natural potential, opportunities and resources of Uzbekistan in the world tourist service market;
- to encourage new innovative approaches aimed at more effective use of ecotourism resources and opportunities of regions, especially nature, geosystems, as well as conducting scientific research in this field;
- increasing the importance and share of ecotourism in the development of tourism;

- Fundamental improvement of the quality of ecotourism services in tourism activities introduced in Uzbekistan and rapid increase in the volume of offered ecotourism services;

- creation of scientific, innovative and methodological developments aimed at the development of ecotourism in the future;

Increasing the positive image of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism, the role of ecotourism in the formation of the international image.

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